

Fatigue life of butt welds between plates tapered in thickness – experiments and simulations

Stefanie Röscher^{*a}, Marion Rauch^b, Markus Knobloch^a

^aRuhr-Universität Bochum, Chair of Steel Lightweight and Composite Structures, Bochum, Germany
stefanie.roescher@rub.de, markus.knobloch@rub.de

^bHochschule Kaiserslautern, Germany
marion.rauch@hs-kl.de

ABSTRACT

Flange thickness transitions are a common constructional detail for a material- and cost-effective design of long span steel girders. With the execution in infrastructure such as bridges, this leads to the fatigue prone detail of a supported, transverse butt weld between centrally or eccentrically arranged flanges of girders, whereas the latter is preferred to allow an easy assembly with incremental launching. The fatigue behaviour of supported joints with eccentrically arranged thickness transitions is complex, and the currently existing experimental background is very limited. In this paper, the results of 30 notch detail tests of butt welds between plates of the same thickness as well as plates tapered in thickness are presented in detail. The tested specimens made of mild steel S355 J2 show application oriented relevant dimension with plate thicknesses between 25 mm and 60 mm. The execution quality and weld geometry have been systematically investigated using 3D scans. The fatigue test results demonstrate that all specimens reveal a significant initiation life, although notch effect and applied loading are high. The performed notch detail tests with an eccentric design reproduce the stress distribution of a supported joint and indicate a higher fatigue resistance compared to a centric design. The detail category of DC 90 given in FprEN1993-1-9:2024 can be confirmed. Further, a corresponding combined analytical and numerical study using the Two-Stage-Model for the fatigue assessment is presented. By a comparison of the test results with the prediction of the Two-Stage-Model, the applicability of the Two-Stage-Model as an advanced fatigue assessment for welded details can be confirmed.

Keywords: Fatigue, notch detail tests, flange thickness transition, Two-Stage-Model

1 INTRODUCTION

Flange thickness transitions are a common constructional detail for a material- and cost-effective design of long span steel girders by adapting the cross section to the bending moment distribution according to the design requirements. With the execution of flange thickness transitions in infrastructure such as bridges, the detail is subjected to fatigue loading. This leads to the fatigue prone detail of a supported, transverse butt weld between centrally or eccentrically arranged flange plates of girders. Within bridge design, often a “flush with the outer surface” execution is chosen to allow an easy assembly with incremental launching, which leads to an eccentric design of the transverse butt weld. The detail of the supported joint, as it occurs in girders, shows a complex load bearing behaviour as well as fatigue behaviour, that differs significantly to the one of unsupported or centric joints (1, 2). Within the research project FATTGirder (3) this difference, also in combination with an additional cope hole, is comprehensively analysed based on large-scale tests and a corresponding advanced fatigue assessment. In this paper, the notch detail tests, which were conducted within this project, are investigated in detail and the results of the performed fatigue tests as well as the corresponding fatigue assessment using the Two-Stage-Model (4–7) are presented.

This paper gives first an overview of the existing experimental databases of notch detail tests for butt welds between plates tapered in thickness. Then, the own performed notch detail tests with centric and eccentric design are presented including the description of the test setup and measurement program as well as the investigations on the execution quality and weld geometry based on 3D scans. The test results of these notch detail tests are presented, showing the total fatigue life as well as the initiation life separately. By a comparison of the test results with the fatigue life prognosis, the applicability of the Two-Stage-Model as an advanced fatigue assessment for welded details is demonstrated.

2 EXISTING EXPERIMENTAL DATABASE

For civil engineering structures, such as bridges, the easy-to-use nominal stress concept is commonly used for the fatigue assessment. The required detail categories (DC) are given for typical constructional details, for example, in EN 1993-1-9:2010 (8) as well as in FprEN1993-1-9:2024 (9) and are based on the statistical evaluation of experimental results. The existing database for transverse butt welds connecting two plates with the same plate thickness, is enormous and contains more than 2800 test results (e.g. (10)). The corresponding constructional detail for transverse butt welds welded from both sides is classified in the detail categories DC 80, 90 or 112, depending on the weld execution (Tab. 10.4, Details 1 to 3 in (9)). The classification of the constructional detail “butt weld between plates tapered in width or thickness” is given for a slope $\leq 1:4$ with DC 90 or 112, also depending on the weld execution (Tab. 10.4, Details 18, 19 in (9)). However, the underlying database of this constructional detail tapered in width or thickness is based on a limited number of experiments from Berger (11).

In (11), Berger presented results from notch detail tests of specimens with a centric design consisting of a tapering in thickness with the slope of 1:4 or a tapering in width with 1:5 to both sides, as summarized in Fig. 1. A statistical evaluation according to EN1990:2010 (12) of these 41 test results (blue markers) leads to a characteristic fatigue resistance of $\Delta\sigma_C = 83 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the specimens with a centric design and in as-welded conditions for a fixed slope of $m = 3$. This evaluation indicates that a tapering with the ratio of 1:4 in centric joints does not fully allow the same categorization as a butt weld between plates of the same thickness with a flank angle $\geq 150^\circ$ (DC 90), although this interpretation is based on a limited number of tests from only one source. Nevertheless, the categorization of centric and eccentric butt welds between plates tapered in thickness is given in FprEN 1993-1-9:2024 (9) by DC 90 with the additional requirement “weld toes blended smoothly” for DC 90 or “ground flush” to allow DC 112.

Fig. 1. Statistical evaluation of fatigue tests from Berger (11) and Zong et al. (13)

In (13), Zong et al. presented the results of notch detail tests on 26 small scale specimens with an eccentric thickness transition ($t_2/t_1 = 12/8 \text{ mm}$). The test results are also summarized in Fig. 1 (green markers) and the statistical evaluation leads to characteristic fatigue resistance of $\Delta\sigma_C = 114 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for $m = 3$ for this detail in as-welded conditions. It has to be mentioned, that the notch detail tests

were conducted within a uniaxial testing machine, but the details regarding the offset are not specified. Thus, it must be assumed, that the setup within a uniaxial testing machine is not adapted to the eccentricity and instead the offset of 2 mm is equalized with bending in the specimen. Furthermore, the load range is given with the nominal stress range instead of the modified nominal stress range. The results indicate a relatively high fatigue resistance for eccentric joints compared to the existing detail category of DC 90 according to FprEN1993-1-9:2024 (9).

These results from Berger (11) and Zong et al. (13) indicate the need of further investigations concerning the often-executed detail “butt weld between plates tapered in width or thickness” for an eccentric design. This correlates with the investigation of the detail “flange thickness transition”, where an eccentric and supported design occurs regularly e.g. in I-section steel girders of long span bridges. To bridging the gap, the here presented experimental investigations and corresponding analytical and numerical study demonstrate the results of specifically designed eccentric notch detail tests, that are also able to reproduce a stress distribution as it occurs in girders with flange thickness transitions.

To illustrate the necessity of an eccentric test setup, Fig. 2a) shows a comparison of a numerically obtained longitudinal stress distribution at the surface of centrally and eccentrically connected plates tapered in thickness. A specimen with the centric design shows a lower stress gradient (red line) compared to an eccentric design (blue line), due to bending in case of an eccentric design. This can be assessed using the modified nominal stress range based on a stress concentration factor. Additionally, the comparison of the longitudinal stress distribution for a girder with flange thickness transition (FTT) in combination with and without a cope hole is given in Fig. 2b). The blue line indicates the stress distribution for an unsupported butt weld with eccentric execution of the connecting plates. The green (variant without cope hole) and orange (variant with cope hole) lines refer to a stress distribution at the inner surface of the flange in an I-section girder with flange thickness transition under pure bending. The comparison shows that an eccentric specimen can reproduce the stress gradient of a supported detail with FTT, which is relevant for practice, sufficiently.

Fig. 2. Stress distribution of the longitudinal stresses at the surface: a) centric and eccentric design for plates tapered in thickness; b) unsupported, eccentrically joined plates tapered in thickness and I-section girder with flange thickness transition (FTT) without and with cope hole

3 FATIGUE TESTS OF CENTRIC AND ECCENTRIC NOTCH DETAILS

3.1 Overview and test specimens

The experimental investigations are part of the research project FATTGirder (3). The presented tests include notch detail tests on butt welds connecting plates of the same thickness as reference as well as eccentrically connected plates tapered in thickness with different thickness ratios. The research includes accompanying material characterization tests for the static and cyclic material properties for the base material of the steel plates as well as high resolution 3D scans of all test specimens before testing to evaluate the local weld geometry and assess the stress concentration factor.

In total 30 specimens consisting of steel with a grade of S355 J2 are investigated in five series with six specimens each. Two series (Series A and D, centric) contain plates of the same thickness and three series (Series B, C and E, eccentric) consist of butt welds connecting plates of different thicknesses eccentrically. The thicker plate is tapered in thickness by a ratio of 1:4, see Fig. 3. Table 1 gives an overview of the test series and the specimen dimensions. The specimen design is based on the application range in bridge design. In particular, the plate thicknesses are chosen between 25 mm and 60 mm, to reproduce practical applications. The welding between two plates has been performed by an industrial partner with typical multi-layer X-welds to obtain and investigate realistic residual stresses and geometrical imperfections. The individual specimens are cut out from the welded plates using water jet cutting. The width of the specimens is chosen with 62.5 or 80 mm to allow a two-dimensional crack growth.

Table 1. Overview of notch detail tests and specimen dimension

Series	t_1 [mm]	t_2 [mm]	t_2/t_1	k_f
A	25	25	1.0	1.00
B	25	40	1.6	1.60
C	25	50	2.0	1.78
D	40	40	1.0	1.00
E	40	60	1.5	1.53

Fig. 3. Illustration of test specimens and applied strain gauges

The applied load range in terms of the nominal stress range ΔS for the thinner plate varies between 90 and 200 N/mm². The stress range is chosen high enough to ensure the fatigue life in the high cycle fatigue regime with $N_f > 100,000$ cycles and to keep at the same time the test duration in an adequate time. The upper load F_{max} is limited by the capacity of the testing machine of $F_{max,dyn} = 0.8$ MN. In addition, the maximum, modified nominal stress is limited to the tensile strength of the utilized material, to ensure a fatigue failure with only small areas of plasticization. The stress ratio $R = S_{min}/S_{max}$ is based on common load situations for infrastructures such as bridges and varies from 0.2 to 0.5.

3.2 Test execution and measurement program

The notch detail tests are conducted at KIBKON laboratory at Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany, using a servo hydraulic universal testing machine. The eccentricity is incorporated in the test setup to reproduce the longitudinal stress distribution and stress gradient of flange thickness transitions including the influences of local bending. Therefore, the fixed clamping is shifted by the offset of the specimens on one side. The notch detail tests are conducted as fatigue tests with constant amplitude loading. The test frequency varies between 4 to 7 Hz. Failure was reached when the stiffness degradation led to an extension of deformation of at least 0.7 mm. This results in a crack with the size of approximately 60 to 70 % of the cross section, see Fig. 4c) exemplarily.

Fig. 4. a) Test specimen with eccentric design in experimental setup; b) specimen with applied strain gauges and FOS; c) crack shape after failure

The strain is measured with 3 mm linear strain gauges with a measurement frequency of 300 Hz 8 mm away from the weld toe (see Fig. 3 and 4b)). For each load cycle the minimum and maximum values

(peak values) of strain are recorded. A significant change in the peak values over the time serves as an indicator for a fatigue induced crack growth. For one specimen of each series, the strain measurement was supplemented with either a digital image correlation (DIC) measurement or a fibre optical system (FOS), see Fig. 4a) and b).

3.3 Material characterization

The plate material is characterized with in-house material testing at Ruhr-University Bochum as well as Hochschule Kaiserslautern. For the base material, the static material properties are obtained from quasi-static tensile tests. The tensile strength amounts to $R_{m,25mm} = 593 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the 25 mm thick plates and $R_{m,40mm} = 546 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the 40 mm thick plates for a steel with a grade of S355 J2. To obtain the cyclic material properties incremental step tests, e.g. (14), have been performed to determine the cyclic strength coefficient K' and the cyclic strain hardening exponent n' . The further parameters, which are needed to fully describe the cyclic material behaviour and resistance (σ_f' , b , ϵ_f' , c) are determined using the compatibility condition and the correlations within the Uniform Material Law (15).

Additionally, the hardness was analysed for the weld profiles using a Vickers hardness HV10. As demonstrated in (16), the Hardness Method (17) is an alternative simplified and suitable approach to obtain the cyclic material properties not only of the base material but also of the weld material and heat effected zone. The hardness tests confirmed the increase of the hardness and therefore also of the cyclic strength coefficient K' of the weld material and heat effected zone compared to the base material with a mean value of 167 HV10. Detailed results of the material characterization tests are given in (3).

3.4 Execution quality and weld geometry based on 3D scans

The execution and weld quality of the specimens affects the fatigue resistance and is implicitly considered within the fatigue tests. The global imperfections “offset” and “angular misalignment” affect the applied stress range, while the local weld geometry affects the notch effect. To evaluate these in detail, all 30 specimens were scanned before testing using the commercial fringe projection scanner ATOS, as shown exemplarily in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Visualization of the local weld geometry based on 3D scans

A detailed investigation shows that all specimens inhabit only a small angular misalignment and offset. The angular misalignment is smaller than 0.4° . Only for series E, single values reach up to 0.7° , but the average remains by 0.4° . The unplanned offset (misalignment between plates) is smaller than 1.0 mm for all specimens. This indicates a generally high execution quality. For Series A and D, the offset leads to an increase in stress range, especially with the introduced bending, while the offset of the eccentric series (Series B, C and E) changes the planned offset of several millimetres only by a small amount. Additionally, the absolute offset of 1 mm is less relevant for series with a higher planned offset.

An overview of the local weld geometry is given with Fig. 5 for one specimen of each series. The scanned surface is analyzed regarding the local weld geometry in 1 mm steps along the longitudinal direction of the weld. With focus on the fatigue life, especially the initiation life N_i , the weld radius r and the weld angle θ are the most determining factors concerning the notch effect and thus of the crack initiation position as well as the initiation life. For Series A and D, all four weld toes are investigated as they are all possible failure locations. For Series B, C and E, only the decisive weld

toe is analysed (weld toe at the thinner plate of the sloped surface). The results of weld angle θ and weld toe radius r are given by a statistical evaluation (mean value and standard deviation) of the stepwise evaluation for the five different series, see Tab. 2. The evaluation indicates the expected approximately normally distributed geometry parameters. The weld radius exhibits a mean value between 0.50 and 0.67 mm, which is within the expected range of 0.5 to 1 mm for MAG welding. The mean flank angle is determined between 163.6° and 170.7° . The obtained geometry parameters have been used to assess the stress concentration factor individually for each specimen. In summary, the investigation of the global and local geometry confirms a high execution quality and allows an individual assessment of the crack initiation life for all specimens (see 4).

Table 2. Geometry parameters of the local weld geometry (mean value and standard deviation)

Series		A	B	C	D	E
r_{mean}	[mm]	0.67	0.50	0.51	0.55	0.53
r_{std}	[mm]	0.32	0.18	0.33	0.17	0.25
θ_{mean}	[$^\circ$]	163.6	164.8	170.7	167.3	167.5
θ_{std}	[$^\circ$]	6.0	4.3	3.7	4.3	5.8

3.5 Fatigue test results

Within the fatigue tests, the specimens exhibit a fatigue induced failure due to crack growth (crack initiation and crack propagation) at the butt weld. The crack initiates at the weld toe of the butt weld for all specimens of the notch detail tests. However, the location of the crack initiation and the resulting crack shape varied along the longitudinal direction of the weld. In the following, first, the test results are presented in terms of number of cycles for the total fatigue life in 3.5.1. Afterwards the distinction between crack initiation and crack propagation is made in 3.5.2.

3.5.1 Total fatigue life

For 24 of 30 specimens, a fatigue-induced failure in form of a crack was observed between 251,300 and 2,369,700 cycles. Six specimens did not show any measurable crack or change in strain after $5 \cdot 10^6$ cycles, and are defined as runouts, as the applied load range did not lead to failure. In Fig. 6, the test results of the performed notch detail tests are shown in the S-N_f diagram in blue markers for the specimens with centric design and green markers for the ones with eccentric design for the total fatigue life N_f. The load range is given as the envisaged modified nominal stress range $\Delta S_{\text{mod}} = N/A \cdot k_f$ based on the nominal cross section A. The data is complemented with 45 recent results from own notch detail tests of transverse butt welds in centric specimens connecting two plates of either 10, 20 or 35 mm, that were investigated within the research project FutureWind (18). The specimens were made of a similar steel grade of S355 J2+N. These results are given by unfilled blue markers. As a comparison, but not included in the statistical evaluation, the results of the existing data of Berger and Zong et al. (11, 13) are also presented in Fig. 6 and shown by grey, unfilled markers.

Fig. 6. S-N_f diagram of notch detail tests and statistical evaluation

The presented statistical evaluation is given for a fixed slope of $m = 3$ based on the statistical evaluation according to EN1990:2010 (12) and distinguishes between the centric (green) and eccentric (blue) specimens. The statistical evaluation of the notch detail tests according to Fig. 6 with centric design leads to a characteristic fatigue resistance of $\Delta\sigma_{C,centric} = 91.6 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for as-welded specimens. This correlates well with the existing database for transverse butt welds as given in literature, where a characteristic fatigue resistance of $\Delta\sigma_C = 89 \text{ N/mm}^2$ is given (10). Thus, it can be concluded that realized test setup, weld quality and plate material comply with a typical execution of existing notch details.

The test results shown in Fig. 6, exhibit a high scattering, which can also be observed by the difference of the 50 % and 95 % characteristic S- N_f curves. The results of the notch detail tests with eccentric design indicate a higher fatigue resistance than the ones with centric design for unsupported butt welds. The statistical evaluation of the new test results of eccentric specimens leads to $\Delta\sigma_{C,eccentric} = 119.4 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the presented tests ($n = 18$) and to $\Delta\sigma_{C,eccentric} = 112.3 \text{ N/mm}^2$ with consideration of additional 21 test results from Zong et al. (13). The higher fatigue resistance compared to the centric design can be explained with the stress gradient over the plate thickness, but also with a high execution and weld quality of this test series (see 3.4). The evaluation confirms the existing classification for butt welds between plates tapered in thickness with DC 90 for an eccentric design. Further tests should be conducted in the future to increase the database and confirm this hypothesis.

3.5.2 Crack initiation and crack propagation life

To investigate the fatigue behavior more detailed, it is desirable to distinguish between the phenomenological phases of crack initiation and crack propagation for the fatigue test results. This allows a more precise evaluation and assessment as well as better basis for a comprehensive validation of advanced fatigue assessment models. Typically, the initiation life N_i is mainly governed by the notch effect due to the local weld geometry, while the ratio of N_i/N_f or N_p/N_f depends on the notch effect as well as applied stress range.

During the fatigue test, the start of crack growth can be reliably detected based on a change in strain before the crack is visible. To identify the number of cycles for crack initiation N_i , the measured strain is normalized, and the initiation life N_i is defined when a change in strain of 5 % is reached. For specimen B.1 for example, the initiation life results to $N_i = 367,300$, when the first strain gauge exceeds a change of 5 %, while the total fatigue life of the specimen is reached at $N_f = 562,000$, see Fig. 7b). This leads to the ratio of $N_i/N_f = 0.66$, indicating a relatively high share of initiation life for this welded constructional detail with a high notch effect and high stress range of $\Delta S_{mod} = 191 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The evaluation of the initiation life N_i based on the change in strain is given in Fig. 7a) for all specimens and indicates that the initiation life N_i shows a high share, which is always more than 40 % of the total fatigue life N_f . The mean value of the ratio of N_i/N_f is determined with $N_i/N_f = 0.61$ for the centric specimens (without runout). Whereas the mean value of the ratio is increased for the eccentric design to $N_i/N_f = 0.68$ (without runouts), indicating a higher initiation life for the eccentric specimens. Within this experimental study, the expected correlation of the ratio N_i/N_f and the applied stress range can be confirmed for all Series, except Series A. Further Details are given in (3).

Fig. 7. a) Ratio N_i/N_f for all specimens; b) Evaluation of strain increase for specimen B.1

4 ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL ASSESSMENT

4.1 Two-Stage-Model for Fatigue Life Prediction of welded details

The Two-Stage-Model is an advanced analytical-numerical fatigue life prediction method, which can be used to assess the total fatigue life. The model differentiates between the crack initiation and crack propagation phase using the strain life and the crack propagation approach. In particular, the geometry and material characteristics of an investigated specimen can be considered individually in both phases. Further information for the application of the Two-Stage-Model for the fatigue assessment of welded details can be found e.g. in (4–7). In the following, the results of the fatigue assessment using the Two-Stage-Model are presented for the notch detail tests.

4.1.1 Input parameters

For the application of the strain life approach in the initiation phase, the cyclic material properties, obtained with corresponding material characterization tests as described in 3.3, are implemented. For an individual assessment of the initiation life of each tested specimen, the notch effect of the local weld geometry was determined analytically based on the geometry parameters obtained from the 3D scan. Though, for the determination of representative S-N_f curves for a whole series, the local weld geometry was approximated with a fictitious notch radius of $\rho_f = 1.0$ mm in combination with a flank angle of 150° (4, 7). The elastic-plastic notch behavior is assessed with the extended Neuber rule according to Seeger and Heuler (19, 20). The fatigue resistance is assumed with the material dependent strain-life curve in combination with the damage parameter P_{SWT} (21). Residual stresses are not considered explicitly, since the tests are executed with a positive R-value. The combination of a fictitious notch radius, the extended Neuber rule and the damage parameter P_{SWT} leads to a suitable assessment for welded details for a positive R-ratio without consideration of residual stresses, as shown in (7). The size effect of the specimen is assessed based on the highly stressed weld length (22). The surface roughness is assumed for an unprocessed surface with R_z = 200 μm. This combination leads to a size effect of 1/f = 0.88 to 0.91 for the 30 specimens and is reducing the fatigue life prediction compared to a small, polished specimen. In the propagation phase, the crack propagation approach is used within a numerical framework using X-FEM based on linear elastic fracture mechanics. The initial crack size is assumed with a_{initial} = 0.5 mm and a/c = 0.5 at the position of the maximum notch stress. The material properties for the crack propagation law are taken from (3) for a similar steel S355J2+N with the Paris law parameters C = 3.215 · 10⁻¹³ and m = 2.93. The failure criterion is taken analogous to the experimental results.

4.1.2 Results of the Two-Stage-Model

The results of the fatigue life prognosis are presented in terms of the initiation life N_i and total fatigue life N_f. First, the initiation life is analysed in detail and the detailed existing experimental data (N_i, cyclic material properties, local weld geometry) allow a reliable assessment and validation. The initiation life N_i is obtained for each specimen individually. Therefore, the notch factor K_t is determined on the scanned weld geometry and the applied stress range extracted from strain measurements. The material properties from the base material are used within the assessment. The predicted initiation life is compared with the experimental results in Fig. 8a). The evaluation demonstrates that the prognosis of the initiation life N_i shows a conservative assessment (expect one result) with an acceptable accuracy.

To evaluate the total fatigue life, the S-N_f curves are obtained with the Two-Stage-Model and given in Fig. 8b) for a reference specimen for each series to allow an assessment of usually existing and varying weld geometry with generally valid S-N_f curves. The notch effect is obtained for an approximated weld geometry ($\rho_f = 1.0$ mm, $\theta = 150^\circ$) as mentioned above. The S-N_i and S-N_f diagrams are given for the modified nominal stress range ΔS_{mod} for an average R-ratio of 0.3 only to enhance clarity. Within the presented evaluation, the linear elastic fracture mechanics approach is applied for all load ranges, which may lead to larger plastic zones at the crack tip.

Fig. 8b) shows the obtained S-N_i curves for the five series and confirms, that a difference in the notch effect leads to significant variation in the predicted initiation life. However, the resulting S-N_f curves show only smaller differences. Especially for higher stress ranges, the fatigue life is governed by the propagation life, and all curves follow the slope of the material parameter m, resulting in parallel curves. For the specimens with failure at the 25 mm thin plates (Series A, B, C), the S-N_f curves show a distinct nonlinear behaviour for lower stress ranges, indicated with a significant change in the slope of the S-N_f curves. For Series D and E, with failure at the 40 mm plate, the S-N_f curves do not show a pronounced change in the slope of the S-N_f curves.

The comparison to the experimental results N_f (filled markers) shows a good agreement for the eccentric specimens, while the assessment of the centric specimens, especially for Series A (green markers), shows partly an unconservative prediction of the total fatigue life. For the evaluation, it has to be considered that the fracture mechanics material properties are only estimated and can significantly affect the prediction. Further, the experimental results contain varying stress ratios from 0.2 to 0.5 and the presented S-N_f curves are given for an enhanced clarity only for R=0.3.

The obtained S-N_f curves correspond very well for high stress ranges with the 50 % S-N curve for centric specimens as given in Fig. 6. Based on the results of the Two-Stage-Model, a better fatigue performance of the eccentric specimens cannot be confirmed so far. However, the results of the propagation phase, and therefore the total fatigue life, will be revised once the corresponding fracture mechanics parameters are obtained.

Fig. 8. a) Comparison of experimental results $N_{i,Experimental}$ and individual fatigue life prediction $N_{i,Prognosis}$; b) S-N_i and S-N_f curves for different Series A to E (R=0.3) and comparison with experimental results

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the results of 30 notch detail tests of butt welds between plates of the same thickness as well as plates tapered in thickness are presented in detail. The chosen test setup included the eccentricity to investigate a stress state comparable to the one in supported butt welds as it occurs in the fatigue prone detail “girder with thickness transition”. The test results confirmed the existing categorization of detail category DC 90 for the application within the nominal stress concept. The tested specimens exhibited an even higher fatigue resistance, which is partly related to the excellent weld and execution quality. Further tests are recommended to cover the entire range of execution quality as allowed within (9). Within the superior research project FATTGirder, the tests enabled a cross reference to conducted full-scale girder tests covering the detail flange thickness transition.

The advanced fatigue assessment using the Two-Stage-Model for welded details could reproduce the test results with sufficient accuracy. A very good agreement was found for the initiation life, which highlights the applicability of the strain life approach for the assessment of welded details.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research presented in this work is based on the research project IGF 21739 N “Ermüdung von Gurt dickensprüngen geschweißter Träger mit Stegausschnitt (FATTGirder)” from the German

Committee for Steel Construction (DAST), Düsseldorf, which is supported by the Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action through the German Federation of Industrial Research Associations (AiF) as part of the programme for promoting industrial cooperative research (IGF) on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag. The project was carried out at Ruhr-Universität Bochum and Hochschule Kaiserslautern.

REFERENCES

1. **Taras, A., Unterweger, H.** Proposal for a stress modification factor for the fatigue design of flange thickness transitions in welded girders. *Engineering Structures*. 2013, 56, 1758-1774.
2. **Unterweger, H., Taras, A., Puig, M. G.** Gurtdickensprünge geschweißter Biegeträger – Bemessungsbehelf für die komplexen lokalen Zusatzbeanspruchungen. *Stahlbau*. 2014, 83(8), 542-552.
3. **Röscher, S., Knobloch, M., Rauch, M.** Ermüdung von Gurtdickensprüngen geschweißter Träger mit Stegausschnitt (FATTGirder). Abschlussbericht IGF Nr. 21739 N, exp. 2024.
4. **Röscher, S., Knobloch, M.** Towards a prognosis of fatigue life using a Two-Stage-Model. *Steel Construction*. 2019, 12(3), 198-208.
5. **Bissing, H., Knobloch, M., Rauch, M.** Advanced fatigue assessment – the future of wind turbine towers. *Procedia Structural Integrity*. 2022, 38, 372-381.
6. **Knobloch, M., et al.** Erweiterte Methoden der Betriebsfestigkeit. In: *Stahlbau-Kalender 2024. Schwerpunkt: Eurocode 3 – Anwendungsnormen*. Berlin: Ernst & Sohn, 2024.
7. **Röscher, S.** Zur erweiterten Lebensdauerprognose geschweißter Strukturen mit dem Zwei-Phasen-Modell. Dissertation. Bochum, 2024.
8. **EN 1993-1-9:2010-12.** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-9: Fatigue.
9. **FprEN 1993-1-9:2024.** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-9: Fatigue. Document CEN/TC 250/SC 3 N 3957
10. **Feldmann, M., et al.** Neubewertung und Erweiterung des Kerbfallkataloges nach Eurocode 3 für eine zukunftsfähige Auslegung hochbeanspruchter Stahlkonstruktionen. Abschlussbericht IGF-Nr. 19178, 2019.
11. **Berger, P.** Zur Tragfähigkeit von Stumpfnähten bei Ermüdungsbeanspruchung. *Schweißtechnik*. 1984, 34(9), 410-414.
12. **EN 1990:2010-12.** Eurocode: Basis of structural design.
13. **Zong, L., Shi, G., Wang, Y.-Q., Zhou, H.** Fatigue assessment on butt welded splices in plates of different thicknesses. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 2017, 129, 93-100.
14. **Vormwald, M.; Seeger, T.** Nutzung der Anrißschwingspielzahl beim Incremental-Step-Test zur Abschätzung der Werkstoffwöhlerlinie. *Materials Testing*. 1988, 30(11-12), 368-373.
15. **Bäumel, A., Seeger, T., Boller, C.** Materials data for cyclic loading. Supplement 1. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1990. *Materials science monographs*. 61.
16. **Rauch, M.** Simplified approaches for material characterization – an alternative for advanced fatigue design methods. *ce/papers*. 2023, 6(3-4), 2412-2417.
17. **Roessle, M., Fatemi, A.** Strain-controlled fatigue properties of steels and some simple approximations. *International Journal of Fatigue*. 2000, 22(6), 495-511.
18. **Knobloch, M., Rauch, M.** Prognosemodelle zur Lebensdauer und zum Weiterbetrieb von Windenergieanlagen (FutureWind). Abschlussbericht IGF Nr. 20987 N, 2023.
19. **Seeger T.; Heuler P.** Generalized Application of Neuber's Rule. *Journal of Testing and Evaluation*. 1980, 8(4), 199-204.
20. **Neuber, H.** Theory of stress concentration for shear-strained prismatical bodies with arbitrary nonlinear stress-strain law. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*. 1961.
21. **Smith, K. N., Watson, P., Topper, T. H.** A Stress–Strain Function for the Fatigue of Metals. *Journal of Materials*. 1970, 5(4), 767-778.
22. **Rudorffer, W., et al.** Modellierung von Schweißnähten zum Nachweis der Ermüdungsfestigkeit mit dem Örtlichen Konzept. AiF Abschlussbericht Nr. 20025 N, 2021.